

Additional file 8: Table S5. Antibodies.

Antibody	Dilution	Reference/source	Identifier
anti-DIG-POD	1:300	Roche Diagnostics AG	11 207 733 910
anti-Fluorescein-POD	1:300	Roche Diagnostics AG	11 426 346 910
rabbit-anti-ORCO	1:200	[24]	
guinea pig-anti IR8a	1:300	[26]	RRID:AB_2566833
rabbit anti-GFP	1:1000	Invitrogen (Molecular Probes)	A-6455
chicken anti-GFP	1:1000	Abcam	ab13970
Alexa Fluor 488 goat anti-guinea pig	1:1000	Invitrogen (Molecular Probes)	A11073
Alexa Fluor 488 goat anti-rabbit	1:100	Invitrogen (Molecular Probes)	A11034
Alexa Fluor 488 goat anti-chicken	1:1000	Abcam	ab150169